

Strategic Conflict Management in Managing Gender Diversity: A Study of PTCL Hyderabad, Sindh (Pakistan)

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Abstract:

The study is to look into the effect of strategic conflict management in managing gender diversity a case of PTCL (Pakistan Telecommunication Limited) in Hyderabad region. The focus of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of conflict resolution styles in organizational culture based on gender diversity. This instrument has developed five types of managing conflict, namely avoiding, integrating, obliging, compromising, and dominating, by incorporating dual dimensions, i.e., self-concern and concern for others. The compromising, obliging, and integrating approach has a positive correlation to gender diversity. All of these types increase effectiveness. To maintain a healthy relationship, organizations must find out how to remove and replace the discriminatory practices that contribute to oppression-based diversity conflict. The key findings of this study suggest that companies that encourage diversity in the workplace motivate employees to perform well. Furthermore, bias recruitment, selection, role allocation, pay, and performance are the main reasons of organizational conflict. From the above research it is concluded that Management is playing a vital role in order to decrease conflicts at workplace, properly managed conflict can improve group outcomes. When organizations apply these three styles, it will keep workers happy and motivated without having a negative effect on their performance.

Keywords: Conflict management styles, Gender diversity, Employee performance, Pakistan Telecommunication Limited, Management outcomes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, every organization encounter conflicts on a daily basis. The development of these conflicts appears through a series of stages, beginning with antecedent conditions and progressing into manifest dispute. Most people see conflict as fighting, although understanding that there are other sides of conflict as well. (Oxford Dictionary, 2016). Conflict takes place at both individual and collective levels, as individual beliefs, desires, behaviors and goals vary (Oni-Ojo, Iyiola, and Osibanjo, 2014).

Strategic conflict resolution is the practice that appears in organizations to limit the destructive aspects of conflict. Nowadays, mostly organizations face numerous challenges in perspective of conflict situation and those organizations which have larger businesses have conflict management strategies. This mechanism is very important for any organization and plays a positive role in bringing organization towards development and growth. Besides that, the organizations are familiar with trends, strategies and behaviors to cope within the prevailing circumstances as well as when conflicts arise.

Parayitam and Papenhouse, (2016) a few studies argue that the sort of conflict resolution approach to be used depends on the nature, purpose and significance of strategic decisions. In terms of age, gender, religious affiliation, workplaces are becoming increasingly diverse. This representation of diversity has consequences for productivity, performance of organizations (Joubert, 2012; Kirton & Greene, 2016). Therefore, when diversity is effectively managed, workers know more about each other in order to improve interaction among workers. Diversity in the workforce is related with increased structural paybacks (Joubert, 2017) and performance (Choi & Rainey, 2010).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Gender Diversity is inevitable part of organizations and if they are not timely managed can result in loss of time, energy and productivity of the firm. Therefore, it is important to explain how diversity leads to conflict, the measures that can prevent and manage conflict in organizations especially in case of PTCL Hyderabad Region.

III. RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the impact of strategic conflict management in managing gender diversity in PTCL Hyderabad region?

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To explore the impact of gender diversity on employee performance.
- To identify reasons of conflicts in terms of gender diversity in PTCL Hyderabad region.
- To investigate strategies taken by management to handle diversity in PTCL Hyderabad region.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Strategic Conflict Management

Resolution of disputes is essential to maintain organizational safety and collaboration when conflict arises. Rahim (2018) define conflict of management in kind it provides several chances for individual as well group and come up with feedback which is essential to guaranteed decreases the conflict of this nature and minimize chances of reappearance. In addition, Lipsky and Avgar (2018) suggest that the idea of conflict management systems had flooded a quarter of large firms studied.

Currie et al (2016) Awan and Anjum (2015) believed successful conflict resolution could produce positive results such as encouraging conversation, cooperative administration, and daily response and Conflict resolution in good time. They argued unmanaged conflict in exchange could encourage unstable interaction and poor employee behavior that can affect the overall morale of workers leads to lower productivity.

In many organizations, tensions and conflicts occur naturally. Handling and managing confrontation and disagreement in operations of organizations are among the core assignments of management in strategic decision making (Saeed, et al 2014). There are some people who may act in that way which lead to resolution of this tension and conflicts through cooperative behavior and that there are some people, who leave those conflicts unresolved and kindle aggressive behavior (Saeed, 2014).

Therefore, resolution of conflicts is very important for enhancing among employees.

B. Conflict Management Styles:

Management styles are specifically most important factors that influence employee satisfaction (Mehrad, 2015). The use of specific strategies could be useful in shaping satisfaction of job, and one of them is conflict resolution styles that managers can employ (Mehrad, 2015) That is because the association among conflict and certain variables will have an effect on the organization, which cannot be denied because it will promote fruitful and creative interaction among the organization's members (Hussein et al., 2017). Furthermore, poor conflict management can result in a variety of negative outcomes, including dissatisfaction, employee turnover, discouragement, and lower productivity. Identifying the conflict and its dimensions is essential managed sensibly, and then improving and leading the company to achieve its objective (Hussein et al., 2017). Leffel, Hallam, and Darling (2012) identify dispute managing as not only conflict resolution, but through approaches like negotiation, collaboration, avoidance, competition, and agreement resolve the element of discord and increase productive effectiveness. The organizational dispute resolution proxies for instance compromise, collaboration, avoidance, competition and accommodation are specified bellow.

Compromise:

It refers to each competing party's ability to surrender everything. Each contested part gives up some value. For the sake of, conflict resolution which means "no winner, no loser".

This method had a mild level of concern for itself and others. It is linked to the concept of give-and-take, in which all sides give up something to reach a mutually satisfactory decision. By finding a middle ground, parties involved in a dispute will be able to find a way that will partly satisfy both parties. This method can be used where a general agreement has not been reached; however, it is not appropriate for dealing with issues involving multiple components. (Esmailzadesh et al., 2015). Employees' responses to workplace conflict can leads to job frustration,

companies' engagement, and the desire put out of the company (Thakore, 2013). As a result, it is crucial for workers to understand the successful types that reduce unnecessary tension and provide immediate value to both businesses and groups.

Integrating:

This personality trait entails a high level of consideration towards oneself and others. It also encouraged problem-solving in a group environment. Employees with this type deal personally with disagreement and seek out new and innovative ways to address their own challenges and also the concerns of others. Integrating method yields good results for the groups involved. When a complicated problem arises, the integrating style is the best option since it provides a win-win solution for both sides. According to several reports, integrating seems to be the most desired method of dealing with disagreement (Rahim, 2002; Lu & Wang, 2017). The collaboration, negotiation, and communication mechanism between the conflicting parties are all part of this strategy.

Avoidance:

This is linked to a lack of concern for oneself and others. It's been linked to circumstances involving withdrawal or refusing to address. This type of individual is unable to fulfil both his and her own as well as others' concerns. It may be used to resolve minor problems or to construct a period of time in which a person feels at ease in a particular scenario. This style is inappropriate when the issues are important to a party, when a person is in charge of making decisions, or when a swift action is required to deal with a situation (Rahim, 2002) but a person leaving the location without any conversation (Mehrad, 2015). The technique of avoidance can be called the desire to withdraw from a dispute or to suppress it. Dispute avoidance is a technique requiring a peaceful minimization of conflict.

Dominating:

Despite its effect on the other conflicting party. Simply refers to the desire to satisfy one's desires of value. This personality trait involves a high level of self-interest and a low level of consideration for others this approach is uncommunicative (Blake & Mouton, 1964), and people who do use it usually

use platform to gain their personal gain while minimizing the advantage of others According to Ayyub (2017), people who are confident in their ability to handle dispute tend to use this style. This strategy is effective in situations where a significant problem for the company, or where an adverse decision by a third party will cause harm to this party It's also appropriate when a supervisor has to negotiate with challenging subordinates on a regular basis or has to make routine decisions (Rahim, 2002). When individuals and subordinates have equal authority, this approach is ineffective.

Obligating:

The accommodating approach refers to a mechanism where one competing group is ready to place the interests of the other party on its own. It includes giving up a conflicting group's interest in resolving the conflict Accommodation also happens in order to maintain relationships with the adversary in conflict and in an attempt to maintain peace or gain social advantage to be used later as recommendation. This approach is appropriate when a person is unaware of the problem, when a party is willing to surrender his rights in exchange for anything in the end, or if a person is in a vulnerable state and believes it is preferable to preserve relations with other groups. Combining accommodating styles with others may result in fruitful relationships that could be linked to a certain point (Lee, 2008; Momanyi, 2016). It needed self-sacrifice as well as the need to please others (Rahim, 2002).

C. Gender Diversity:

Gender and diversity, known as the proportion of male and female at workplace, top managerial staff or workers, is beneficial for associations, given that female's entrance into every authoritative level has driven hierarchical advancement and thusly monetary improvement (Besamusca et al., 2015). Men working in organization are commonly use a lot of verbal aggressiveness languages and resulted as insults, put downs, teasing, and practical jokes (Maltz & Borker, 2007). On the other hand, women, are often taught to be interdependent, submissive and to be concerned with relational satisfaction. During interaction, women tend to use a 'we' language, send many signs of interest toward the

other person and give confirming responses (Maltz & Borker, 2007). Therefore, men and women are two different individuals and have so many reasons and have several differences available. Empirical studies have examined how organizational quality is influenced by gender diversity (Low et al., 2015). Nurses experience cultural diversity in Egyptian public hospitals, and one of the key results was that nurses earn lower evaluation rates and feel discriminated only when their supervisors are men (Moussa, 2017).

According to Su et al. (2015), managerial positions perform a significant role in influencing the gender equity context, so they can accurately enforce a strong gender diversity mechanism unless they have adequate power, knowledge, and economic assistance. Employees are increasingly joining organizations that promote diversity and respect differences, according to Kundu and Mor (2017). As a result, businesses have begun to change or update their diversity-related strategies and practices on a regularly in order to achieve an equitable work environment that promotes equality, commitment, empathy, for all employees, regardless of differences.

VI. METHODS:

In conducting research, quantitative approach is used. Quantitative analysis is a form of research that uses analytical evaluations to answer research objectives. It requires the use of numerical calculation and analysis techniques (Zikmund, 2010).

Table 1: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.655	1.731		2.689	.008
	GDIV	3.248	.580	.366	5.597	.000
	GTD	1.999	.267	.448	7.499	.000
	WPM	1.734	.268	.423	6.472	.000

a. Dependent Variable: P

The relationship between gender group and employee performance is significant. Therefore, alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.809a	.655	.644	2.87700

a. Predictors: (Constant), WPM, GTD, GDIV

A. SAMPLE

Total 400 questionnaires were distributed and 302 responses were received by respondents who participated in the research. Overall response rate is 75.2%. Out of which 267 were male and 35 female respondents. Moreover, age of respondents was 20 – 39 years and above.

B. DATA COLLECTION

The survey questionnaire is prime data collection tool in this research. The target group was chosen using a convenience sampling technique. Section A collects demographic information from respondents, including gender, age, position in the company, and working experience. The independent variable in Section B is used to describe the key effect of strategic conflict management styles on gender diversity. Section C is made up of 12 questions on gender diversity. Section D consists of 12 questions that measures employee “performance). In this analysis, the nominal, ordinal, and interval scales (also known as the Likert scale) were used. The survey data was statistically analyzed using the Software Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 16.0 for Student Version).

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

OBJECTIVE # 1: To explore the impact of gender diversity on employee performance.

Hypothesis 1

H1: There is significant relationship between gender diversity and employee performance.

The correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variables is represented by the R value. The correlation coefficient(R) of the independent variable with the dependent variable is 0.809, according to the Model Summary. As a result, the independent variable and dependent variable have a positive and moderate correlation.

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1524.366	3	508.122	61.389	.000 ^b
	Residual	802.881	97	8.277		
	Total	2327.248	100			
a. Dependent Variable: P						
b. Predictors: (Constant), WPM, GTD, GDIV						

The p-value is 0.000, which is less than the alpha value of 0.01. Aside from that, the F-statistic, with a value of 61.389, is significant. As a result, the model perfectly describes the relationship between the dependent and predictor variables. As a result, the independent variables make a significant proportion of the variation in perceived employability. Alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

OBJECTIVE # 2. To identify reasons of conflicts in terms of gender diversity in PTCL Hyderabad region.

H1: There is significant relationship between conflict and gender diversity.

Table 4: Coefficients

Model		Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.788	.966		.816	.417
	GTD	-.514	.143	-.171	-3.595	.001
	GD	.613	.031	.939	19.704	.000
a. Dependent Variable: conflict						

The relationship between conflict and gender diversity is significant. Therefore, alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.895a	.801	.797	1.45271
a. Predictors: (Constant), GD, GTD				

The correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variables is represented by the R value. The correlation coefficient(R) of the independent variable with the dependent variable is

0.895, according to the Model Summary. As a result, the independent variable and dependent variable have a positive and moderate correlation.

Table 6: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	842.535	2	421.268	199.619	.000b
	Residual	208.926	99	2.110		
	Total	1051.461	101			
a. Dependent Variable: conflict						
b. Predictors: (Constant), GD, GTD						

The p-value is 0.000, which is less than the alpha value of 0.01. Aside from that, the F-statistic, with a value of 199.619, is significant. As a result, the

model perfectly describes the relationship between the dependent and predictor variables. Alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

Objective # 3 To investigate strategies taken by management to handle diversity in PTCL Hyderabad region.

H1: There is significant relationship between conflict management styles and gender diversity.

Table 7: Coefficients

Model		Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.277	2.506		7.691	.000
	CSIN	.580	.178	.311	3.254	.002
	CSDOM	.685	.176	.365	3.885	.004
	CSA	.559	.192	.263	2.909	.004

a. Dependent Variable: GD

The relationship between conflict management styles and gender diversity is significant. Therefore, alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.485 ^a	.235	.212	4.38719

a. Predictors: (Constant), CSA, CSDOM, CSIN

The correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variables is represented by the R value. The correlation coefficient (R) of the independent variable with the dependent variable is

0.485, according to the Model Summary. As a result, the independent variable and dependent variable have a positive and moderate correlation.

Table 9: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	579.327	3	193.109	10.033	.000 ^b
	Residual	1886.251	98	19.247		
	Total	2465.578	101			

a. Dependent Variable: GD
b. Predictors: (Constant), CSA, CSDOM, CSIN

The p-value is 0.000, which is less than the alpha value of 0.01. Aside from that, the F-statistic, with a value of 10.033, is significant. As a result, the model perfectly describes the relationship between the dependent and predictor variables. Alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study focused on managing conflict by identifying the conflict handling styles. For addressing diversity conflict issues based on individual differences, integrating conflict management style is useful. The findings of this study shows that discrimination, favoritism and male dominating culture are the main reasons of conflict. It is concluded from the study that majority of the employees are well aware about gender diversity system and it has positive impact on

employee's performance. It has been observed that diverse team perform better than homogenous team. Employees agree that achievement is based on the same performance metrics for men and women.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- ✓ Based on the results of research study, it is recommended that, Diversity management and organizational inclusion play a significant role in shaping and maintaining workplace happiness.
- ✓ It is important for managers to understand the management styles of conflict resolution. The most effective approach for diversity conflict management is to support diversity and inclusion.
- ✓ Diverse teams perform better than homogenous teams.

- ✓ Organizations in firms should always consider the recruiting of female employees to have a gender diverse workforce.
- ✓ Organizations must identify and implement ways to eliminate the systems of inequality that cause oppression-based diversity conflict.

X. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Limitations of Research work:

- This study is restricted to Hyderabad district of Sindh.
- Study mainly focused on diversity management in PTCL Hyderabad.

Future Research Directions:

The author suggests other HR researchers test the same hypotheses in academic side.

- To conduct the identical study by using large sample size.

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- Another could be to study on managing cultural diversity.
- Since our study only focuses on quantitative measure, future works are encouraged in several areas in both quantitative and qualitative measure.

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